

PIRO-2025-02684

Details

Working Title USACE Project Pika Cable Landing Tinian
Request Received Sep 20, 2025

Region PIRO
Division Protected Resources Division (PRD)
Branch Intergovernmental Coordination and Conservation Branch

Activity Details

Category	Sub-Category
Construction	Utility line Installation and Repair

Primary Action Agency

US Department of Defense (DOD) - US Army Corps of Engineers (USACE)

Species Details

Taxa	Common Name	Scientific Name	Listing Unit	Status	Designated Critical Habitat	Foreign
Coral	Coral	<i>Acropora globiceps</i>	Range-wide	Threatened Range-wide	✓	✗
Fish	Scalloped Hammerhead Shark	<i>Sphyrna lewini</i>	Indo-West Pacific DPS	Threatened Indo-West Pacific DPS	✗	✗
Fish	Oceanic Whitetip Shark	<i>Carcharhinus longimanus</i>	Range-wide	Threatened Range-wide	✗	✗
Fish	Giant Manta Ray	<i>Manta birostris</i>	Range-wide	Threatened Range-wide	✗	✗
Turtle	Green Turtle	<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	Central West Pacific DPS	Endangered Central West Pacific DPS	✗	✗
Turtle	Hawksbill Turtle	<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	Range-wide	Endangered Range-wide	✓	✗
Turtle	Leatherback Turtle	<i>Dermochelys coriacea</i>	Range-wide	Endangered Range-wide	✓	✗
Turtle	Loggerhead Turtle	<i>Caretta caretta</i>	North Pacific Ocean DPS	Endangered North Pacific Ocean DPS	✗	✗
Turtle	Olive Ridley Turtle	<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	All Other Areas	Threatened All Other Areas	✗	✗
Whale	Blue Whale	<i>Balaenoptera musculus</i>	Range-wide	Endangered Range-wide	✗	✗
Whale	Fin Whale	<i>Balaenoptera physalus</i>	Range-wide	Endangered Range-wide	✗	✗
Whale	Humpback Whale	<i>Megaptera novaeangliae</i>	Western North Pacific DPS	Endangered Western North Pacific DPS	✓	✗
Whale	Sperm Whale	<i>Physeter macrocephalus</i>	Range-wide	Endangered Range-wide	✗	✗
Whale	Sei Whale	<i>Balaenoptera borealis</i>	Range-wide	Endangered Range-wide	✗	✗

Critical Habitat Details

Taxa	Common Name	Scientific Name	Listing Unit	Status
Coral	Acropora globiceps	<i>Acropora globiceps</i>	Range-wide	Designated <i>Range-wide</i>
Taxa	Common Name	Scientific Name	Listing Unit	Status
Turtle	Green Turtle	<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	Central West Pacific DPS	Proposed ⓘ <i>Central West Pacific DPS</i>

Location Information

Country/International Waters	Foreign Waters Jurisdictional Zone	US Waters Jurisdictional Zone	State/Territory	Body of Water	HUC Level #	HUC Number
United States		State or Territory Waters	Northern Mariana Islands	Philippine Sea	Level 6	220201020000

GIS Information

Type	Label	Lat Degrees	Lat Minutes	Lat Seconds	Lat Decimal	Long Degrees	Long Minutes	Long Seconds	Long Decimal
No GIS details available									